

JOURNAL OF DENTISTRY AND ALLIED SCIENCE

Volume: 02, No: 01

January, 2019

ISSN: 2791-0857

Peer Reviewed Journal

Content

Original Articles

- 1) **Management of Physical Facilities and Utilization of Operation Theatre at Selected Tertiary Level Hospitals in Dhaka City.** 6-11
Qureshi A, Hossain S, Kader MA, Ahmed A,
Akhtar J, Shimu T, Ahmed N, Sultana K N, Ferdous I
- 2) **Treatment Seeking Behavior on Occupational Health Hazard Among Garments Workers in Dhaka City.** 12-17
Akhtar J, Begum E Qureshi A, Noor LA, Ahmed A
- 3) **A Study on Oral Hygiene Status Among Children Attending Pediatric Outpatient Department of City Dental College, Dhaka.** 18-24
Khan MOR, Hasan S M S, Qureshi A, Almajidi WA, Rupa S K, Hasan H

Case Reports

- 1) **Management of Severe Early Childhood Caries in Primary Dentition: A Case Report** 25-29
Nuruzzaman K, Qureshi A, Mannan H,
Chowdhury S, Ahmed A, Akter K N
- 2) **Customized Ocular Prosthesis for Anophthalmic Socket: A Clinical Report.** 30-32
Islam M S, Hossain I, Hossain S, Masud M A,
Rahman MT, Tamij N
- 3) **Orthodontic Treatment of Endodontically Treated Teeth with Prosthesis.** 33-37
Naim M A, Nahar L, Nath B R, Azad MAK, Islam K M.

University Dental College
(A Project of DMCR Foundation)

Management of Severe Early Childhood Caries in Primary Dentition: A Case Report

Nuruzzaman K¹, Qureshi A², Mannan H³, Chowdhury S⁴, Ahmed A⁵, Akter K N⁶

ABSTRACT:

Early childhood caries (ECC) is considered being one of the most common chronic illnesses of children and adolescent. Children with carious primary dentition are in high risk of subsequent caries development in permanent dentition. ECC is not self-limiting disease and need to be intervening in multidisciplinary approach. Management of ECC can only be achieved by definitive oral hygiene care, complete rehabilitation of dentition and preventive care.

Key words: Caries, Deciduous teeth, Early Childhood Caries (ECC)

1. Dr. Khandakar Nuruzzaman
Lecturer
Department of Paediatric Dentistry,
University Dental College, Dhaka
2. Dr. Ashik Qureshi
Associate Professor (C.C) and Head (In
charge)
Department of Paediatric Dentistry,
University Dental College, Dhaka
3. Dr. Huda Mannan
Assistant Professor
Department of Paediatric Dentistry,
University Dental College, Dhaka
4. Dr. Shaila Chowdhury
Associate Professor and Head
Department of Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery
University Dental College, Dhaka
5. Dr. Anam Ahmed
Associate Professor,
Department of Dental Public Health
University Dental College, Dhaka
6. Dr. Kh. Nelufer Akter
Assistant Professor,
Department of Dental Public Health
University Dental College, Dhaka

Address of Correspondence:

Dr. Khandakar Nuruzzaman.
B.D.S (DU), M.Sc. in Pediatric Dentistry (Mahidol
University-Thailand)
Lecturer,
Department of Paediatric Dentistry, University
Dental College and Hospital
Email: knzaman98@gmail.com

INTRODUCTION:

Early childhood caries (ECC) is defined as, the presence of one or more decayed (noncavitated or cavitated lesions), missing (due to caries), or filled tooth surfaces in any primary tooth in a child 71 months of age or younger. Presence of any smooth surface caries younger than the age of 3 years termed as severe early childhood caries (S-ECC).¹ At the age of 5 years decayed, missing and filled surfaces score ≥ 6 also constitutes S-ECC.² ECC is one of the most common chronic diseases of childhood and five times more prevalence than chronic respiratory diseases.³ The interactions between susceptible microorganism, cariogenic substrate, host susceptibility and time responsible for development of ECC. Streptococci mutants and lactobacillus species are chief pathogenic organism for fermentation of carbohydrate substrate.⁴ Management and prevention of ECC considered to be the most difficult and challenging condition for pedodontist.⁵ Increase awareness on prevalence, severity and impact of ECC on overall health is required in order to prevent development of ECC.³ This article represents oral rehabilitation of a child with S-ECC.

CASE REPORT:

A 5.5 years old boy accompanied by his mother with the chief complains of pain on left lower quadrant. Medical history of the child was non-contributory. Past dental history was pulp therapy of anterior tooth from local dental clinic. During clinical examination multiple dental carious lesion were found involving 54, 62, 64, 65, 74, 75 and 84 (FDI method). Among those carious lesions, 74 was grossly decayed and represents pain and sensitivity. Discolored and fractured maxillary central incisors were noticed during clinical examination. Poor oral hygiene status was also noted during examination. The child was rated 'positive' according to Frankle's behavior rating scale. Provisional diagnosis were made child suffers from S-ECC and symptomatic irreversible pulpitis on 74 and, these finding were further confirmed by following radiographic examination (fig: 1.a) Confirmatory diagnosis was made as

symptomatic irreversible pulpitis on 74, pulpectomized tooth on 51 and with dislodged sealer on 61 (fig: 1.b) and S-ECC based on history, clinical examination and radiographic examination.

1st Visit:

Comprehensive treatment planning was made with the consent of parent. At the first visit, single visit pulpectomy were carried out in order to relief pain associated with the symptomatic irreversible pulpitis. Following pulp therapy periapical radiograph were taken to confirm optimum sealing of the canal accompanied with bitewing radiograph of all posterior teeth (fig: 1.c). After finishing pulp therapy, preventive resin restoration was carried out on 75. Oral hygiene instruction was given on child and mother. Moreover, discussion with the parent were made regarding further treatment procedure and provided diet chart for recording dietary history.

(a) Periapical- 74 (b) Periapical- upper anterior (c) Right & left bitewing

Figure 1: Preoperative radiograph

(a) Upper arch (b) Frontal view (c) Lower arch

Figure 2: Preoperative photograph

2nd visit:

During 2nd visit, oral photographic registration (fig:2) was taken before initiation of treatment. Re-pulpectomy was carried out on 51 and 61 followed by stainless steel crown. Sealing status of canal was checked by post sealing radiograph. Resin modified glass ionomer filling was done on 62. After treatment, diet chart was assessed and cariogenic foods were isolated. Parents were advised to reduce cariogenic diet and reduce the frequency of intake of sweet snacks.

3rd visit:

On the 3rd visit all carious lesion was excavated on 64 and 65 followed by preventive

resin restoration on 65 and stainless steel crown on 64. Besides, stainless steel crown fitted on previously pulpectomized tooth 74.

4th visit:

4th visit were constituted resin modified glass ionomer filling on 54 and 84 following complete caries removal. Pit and fissure sealant were applied on 55 and 85 due to high caries risk susceptibility of child. Fluoride varnish was applied on all teeth and re-enforced oral hygiene instructions were given. Photographic registration of oral manifestations following completion of treatment (fig: 3) and radiographs(fig: 4) were taken.

(a) Upper arch

(b) Frontal view

(c) Lower arch

Figure 3: Postoperative photograph

(a) Right & left bitewing

(b) Periapical- upper anterior

Figure 4: Postoperative radiograph

DISCUSSION:

Children experiencing dental caries in primary dentition have a much better probability of developing caries in permanent dentition.⁶ As children are not co-operative enough, management of ECC is much difficult due to behavioral effect of anxiety and fear in children.⁷ Dental Management of ECC focused on regular periodic checkup with topical fluoride application, controlling of plaque and dental restorative care.⁸ Along with the restorative care, successful controlling of risks and factors may leads to prevent initiation, slow down or even arrest progression of dental caries.⁹ Education level and awareness of parents are highly associated with the development and severity of ECC. Lack of proper oral hygiene care, improper brushing technique, less frequency of brushing and use of fluoride toothpaste have greater impact on occurrence of ECC.¹⁰ Restorative treatment of dental caries alone unable to stop disease process unless identification of individual's risk factors for development of dental caries.¹¹ Absence of tooth brushing before bedtime is an important risk factors for development of ECC. As for insufficient manual dexterity of children, parents are recommended to cleanse their pre-school children teeth.¹⁰ The increasing public awareness by parental education regarding proper oral hygiene care, brushing thoroughly twice daily as well as to floss the teeth at least once daily should be advocated by parents.⁸ Application of pit and fissure sealant can be

used as preventive care to prevent development of new carious lesion.⁴ Dental sealants are capable to reduce initiation of new carious lesions and recommended to place in children with high caries risk.¹¹ High fluoride releasing fissure sealants can helps to maintain concentration of fluoride in saliva for longer period of time.¹² Resin modified glass ionomer cement recommended for class I and class II restoration of primary molars while stainless steel crown is recommended following pulp therapy and severe destruction.¹¹ Along with the operative therapy, professional application of topical fluoride is effective in reduction of ECC.²

CONCLUSION:

Early Childhood Caries is not self-limiting disease and would cause severe dental destruction if left untreated. Early diagnosis, limitation of the risks and comprehensive dental care initiated at early age can prevent development of ECC.

REFERENCES:

1. American Academy of Pediatric Dentistry. Definition of Early Childhood Caries (ECC), 2008, 15.
2. American Academy of Pediatric Dentistry. Policy on Early Childhood Caries (ECC): Classifications, Consequences, and Preventive Strategies. Oral Health Policies, 2014, 37(6): 15-16.
3. Shilpashree K.B., Naganadini S. & Ramakrishna T. Management of ECC. Heal Talk, 2012, 4:4.
4. Fung M.H.T., Wong M.C.M., Lo E.C.M. & Chu C.H. Early Childhood Caries: A Literature Review. Journal of Oral Hygiene Health, 2013, 1: 107.
5. Kayalvizhi G., Vishwas T.D., Mahantesh R. & Subramaniyan B. Dental management of severe early childhood caries. El Mednifico Journal, 2014, 2(3): 296-298.
6. Jayam C. Early Childhood Caries. Journal of Indian Dental Association, 2011, 1(1): 11-14.
7. Chu C.H. Treatment of early childhood caries: A review and case report. General Dentistry, 2000, 48(2): 142-8.
8. Ismail A.I. Determinants of Health in Children and the Problem of Early Childhood Caries. Pediatric Dentistry, 2003, 25(4): 328-33.
9. Ng M.W., Ramoz-Gomez F., Lieberman M., Lee J.Y., Scoville R., Hannon C. et al. Disease Management of Early Childhood Caries: ECC Collaborative Project. International Journal of Dentistry, 2014.
10. Zafar S., Harnekar S.Y. & Siddiqi A. Early childhood caries: etiology, clinical considerations, consequences and management. International Dentistry South Africa, 2009, 11(4): 24-36.
11. American Academy of Pediatric Dentistry. Guideline on Restorative Dentistry. Clinical Practice Guideline, 2016, 38(6): 251-62.
12. Nuruzzaman K., Nakornchai S. & Surarit R. Fluoride release of dental sealants following exposure to fluoride toothpaste and fluoride varnish. The 6th Asian Academic Society International Conference, 2018, ISBN: 978-616-470-007-9. Mae Fah Luang University, Thailand.